

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AUTOMATION WELDING PROCESS SYSTEM TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH

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Abstract: Welding systems in technological processes are being changed by the emergence of modern information technologies such as the Internet and things, big data, artificial intelligence, cloud computing and smart manufacturing systems are developing widely. Intelligent welding systems using these technologies are attracting attention from the academic and industrial communities. Intelligent welding is the use of computers to imitate, augment and/or replace human operators sensing, learning, decision making, monitoring and control, etc. This is achieved by combining the advantages of human and physical systems into intelligent cyber systems. Smart welding is found and provides a systematic analysis of experimental applications in industry, its components, applications and future directions helps provide a unified definition of intelligent welding systems. This article examines the main components and techniques needed to make welding systems intelligent, including sensing and signal processing mining and selection, modeling, decision making and learning. Emerging technologies and their application The potential of IWS is also explored, including Industry 4.0, cyber-physical systems, digital twins, and more. Typical applications in IWS including welding design, task sequencing, robot path planning, robots are studied. programming, process monitoring and diagnostics, forecasting, process control, quality inspection and evaluation; human-robot collaboration and virtual welding. Finally, conclusions and suggestions for future development is offered. This review is intended to provide an up-to-date reference for those interested implementation of smart welding capabilities in traditional welding stations, systems and modernization studies of technological processes of factories are considered.

Keywords: Welding in the technological process, artificial intelligence, intelligent manufacturing, robotic welding system, monitoring and control, machine learning research, welding geometry, welding control, computer system processes, Intelligent systems.

Introduction

In technological processes, welding processes and systems play an important role in the stages of modern development and serves to ensure continuous technological processes of industrial production lines. After decades of evolution, many welding operations using hand tools were replaced by an automated system and welding systems with the help of industrial robots have started to be used in the Republic of Uzbekistan. When welding robots, used for decades, they are pre-programmed machines and limited, if any, intelligent system creation forms the stage of technology development. Today's welding processes are complex, with many parameters and limited understanding of the process depends on the mechanism. At the same time, users and customers have special welding requirements and creates a dynamic work environment. Hence welding moving to more customized manufacturing using the next

generation welding systems that can be intelligently adapted to changing welding tasks maintaining high quality is part of our goals and objectives. In the age of big data, it is important to have smart strategies for collecting and sharing welding data, both to improve internal operations and as part of a comprehensive life cycle assessment in industrial supply chains. That is why for example, in-process welding parameters and post-process welding monitoring can help improve the quality of welding processes, components. In technological processes performance and subsequent service quality assurance plays an important role. Although there are many methods of welding, developments in information science and technology are helping to transform the traditional welding craft. and advances in many areas of technological processes computer science, control theory, robotics and artificial intelligence allowing to replace manual work with automation and intelligent technology system is developing. These were concepts and related technologies Explored in manufacturing research initiatives such as Industry 4.0, smart manufacturing, internet of things (IoT), industrial internet, big data, artificial intelligence 2.0, next-generation smart manufacturing and human-cyber-physical systems are creating a model for the future industry. These are initiatives provide the necessary drivers, activators and boards. In addition, it is very important to study the geometry of the weld. In technological processes when there are special technical requirements, such as coating processes, production line cost studies, input waste control and reduction, and process to study the specific characteristics of the components is welded. Azizbek has been conducting research related to measurement and evaluation and of weld geometry in arc welding processes in the past Explores 50 years of development analysis. In this sense, different achievements done In any case, Azizbek claims that it is correct and based on the selection of measurement techniques and algorithms in fusion the use of sensor technologies gives an effective result. Then, in combination with indirect measuring techniques, welding reduces production costs and increases their productivity, therefore reducing the number and rejected parts in final quality control use we can observe that it is based on modern power sources and robotic systems. When controlling weld geometry, width, height and penetration are the main properties considered in various industries. In general, a significant part of the systems has been developed control of geometric parameters during the welding process. In technological processes based on statistical and artificial intelligence models, which usually linear regression and neural networks. In applying such methodologies, the control variables of such proposed systems rely mainly on control power supply variables. For example, typical control variables are voltage and wire feed rate control conventional technological process using constant voltage type it is necessary to organize a power source. Other independent parameters of power the source can be additionally involved, for example, welding speed, contact tip-to-workpiece distance, and shielding gas changes should be considered.

Creation of an intelligent welding system scheme in technological processes

The intelligent welding system of technological processes controls the operations and station, system and systems levels to achieve it different system objectives must be considered. As mentioned above, smart welding at the station level systems are primarily robotic welding systems, but more and more intelligence is moving to the station level, as shown in Picture 1(a) . An in the system configuration example for station-level processes given. Typical tasks pre-welding procedures such as robot planning etc. are conducted in IWS and control, monitoring and control of the welding process is necessary. Multiple station-level IWS

integration over an industrial network improves the free flow of information across a wider range of areas breadth, precision and depth of resource allocation. System level IWS can be in the form of welding production lines, workshops, enterprises, and so on. Several system-level IWSs are integrated at the SoS-level industrial internet and intelligent cloud platforms will be installed. SoS level IWS provides horizontal, vertical and end-to-end integration and platforms, building an industry ecosystem with potential is realized in the processes of openness, synergy and sharing. In the next section, convenient technologies for improvement the performance of tasks is considered. Then, the evolving platform technologies and manufacturing research initiatives are affected and intelligent welding direction is checked. Enabling technologies for IWS Although there are many technologies that support IWS, this is the main focus section is devoted to common enabling technologies including sensors and sensors, signal processing and feature extraction, modeling and simulation, decision making and reasoning, machine study sensors and sensing techniques analog, digital and image signal sensors are combined in welding systems for the quantitative description of welding parameter data. Example parameters of the arc welding process are current, voltage, travel speed, electrode expansion and electrode diameter. You are technology is important for welding modeling and control process acoustic, power, visual. voltage and current signals. Research literature is devoted to this topic the strengths and weaknesses of the sensing technologies shown in Picture 1. In recent years, multi-sensor fusion experimental systems have become available designed to obtain more accurate process data, thus, a more complete, accurate, effective description of the process and can be obtained from one sensor and the continuity of the technological process is ensured.

Picture 1. Scheme of intelligent welding system at the level of technological processes at the station (a) Technological process monitoring and control scheme, (b) Typical structure of the system

Conclusions

As for the geometry of the external system environment of the welds where the technological process is carried out in welding, this research presents a computer vision system followed by a goal-based intelligent system agent. This system allows simultaneous control of the width and height of the weld studies for a technological process in the short-circuit transmission mode without the need for a predefined model made in a special welding process. We conclude that the inference method used in the controller does not represent it and is technological mathematical model of the process, but it can increase or reducing the values of the control variable by the appropriate percentage depending on the errors between the monitored signals and derived from reference values for each geometric parameter. In addition, sensor fusion and real-time monitoring short-circuit transmission regularity index control helps to correct instabilities in technological processes. A computer vision system in the case of penetration, based on a single sensor, it allows segmentation of relevant objects, on the scene and quickly and correctly extracting the necessary items data, so it processes one frame per millisecond. Regarding the vibration frequency of welding processes, the results the frequency spectra show an adequate distribution and behavior as expected. So it can be concluded the methodology is compatible with the monitoring system. In the technological process will depend on the application of an adequate process in obtaining the frequency of oscillation. Accordingly, the modeling procedure developed in technological processes is considered and important as a methodological approach, warranting causes any combination of parameters to support penetration. So, the model offers good looks and quality stitches, creates many opportunities to achieve the desired characteristics. About uncertainty the manager concluded that the technique allowed for error and it is necessary to work according to the system diagram in order to immediately adapt to the changes in properties throughout the welding process. Then, relevant consistency is achieved and working conditions change. Otelbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute under the Navoi State University of Mining and Technologies, is conducting research on the automation of processes in mining enterprises. We can also use automation of technological processes in mining enterprises. For example, we can monitor the mining system using GPS technology, this system works with high accuracy. In mining enterprises, this system ensures the quality and safety of processes. Many of Azizbek's articles on technological processes in mining enterprises have been published in magazines. There is a high level of interest in processes in mining enterprises, metallurgy, chemical processes, the structure of metal melting furnaces, processes such as metal flotation enrichment.

References:

1. Ravshanov Z. 3D Technological System of Management of Geological Exploration Processes of Mining Enterprises //Scienceweb academic papers collection. – 2022.
2. Bekbawlievich S. B. et al. PROSPECTS FOR THE RATIONAL USE OF IRON ORE OF SULTAN UVAYS AT THE TEBINBULAK DEPOSIT //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – T. 9. – №. 12. – C. 609-613.
3. Xolmatov O. M. et al. MURUNTAU KONI OLTINLI RUDALARINI UYUMDA TANLAB ERITISH USULIDA O'ZLASHTIRISHNING GEOTEXNOLOGIK SHAROITLARINI O'RGANISH //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 11. – C. 790-797.

4. Саидова Л. Ш. и др. АНАЛИЗ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ ПО ПОДЪЕМУ ГОРНОЙ МАССЫ ИЗ ГЛУБОКИХ КАРЬЕРОВ И ВЫБОР ГОРНОТРАНСПОРТНОГО ОБОРУДОВАНИЯ ДЛЯ ОТКРЫТЫХ ГОРНЫХ РАБОТ //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 811-816.
5. Ҳайитов О. Ғ. и др. ЧУҚУР КАРЬЕРЛАРДА КОН ЖИНСЛАРИНИ АВТОМОБИЛ ТРАНСПОРТИДА ТАШИШ ИШЛАРИНИ ҲИСОБЛАШ //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 798-803.
6. Saparov A. B. et al. Analysis Of the Effect of The Physical Properties of Liquids on External Forces (Factors) //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2022. – Т. 5. – С. 111-114.
7. Saparov B., Kuyliev T. Spiritual heritage as a worldview factor in the development of society //ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, –pp. – 2020. – С. 69-72.
8. Сапаров Б. Б., Жумамуратов Д. К. ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ АКТИВНЫХ МЕТОДОВ ОБУЧЕНИЯ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ В ВЫСШЕЕ УЧЕБНОМ ЗАВЕДЕНИИ //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 330-333.
9. Bekturganova, Z., & Jumamuratov, R. (2017). МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОЙ РАБОТЕ УЧАЩИХСЯ НА УРОКЕ ХИМИИ.
10. Kaipbergenov A. The methodology of teaching chemistry based on the use of computer programs //Scienceweb academic papers collection. – 2019.
11. Бектурганова, З., Жумамуратов, Р., & Султанов, Д. (2017). РЕКОМЕНДАЦИИ ПО РАЗРАБОТКЕ И ПРОВЕДЕНИЮ С МЕТОДОМ ПРОБЛЕМНОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ НА УРОКАХ ХИМИИ.
12. O'TELBAYEVA Muhayyo Alisherovna. (2023). METHODOLOGY AND THEORY OF CHEMISTRY TEACHING IN SCHOOLS, METHODS AND PROCESSES OF THEIR STUDY. Journal of Experimental Studies, 2(2), 10–16. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7623700>
13. O'TELBAYEVA Muhayyo Alisherovna. (2023). ANALYSIS OF PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL METHODS AND APPROACHES. Pedagogical and Psychological Studies, 2(2), 12–16. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7624764>
14. Yeshmuratova A. MINE BLASTING PROCESSES OPTIMIZATION STAGES OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY OF DETONATORS //Scienceweb academic papers collection. – 2023.
15. Utepbayeva G. et al. FOAM FLOTATION PROCESS, STAGES AND TECHNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. A2. – С. 136-140.
16. Утемисов А. О., Юлдашова Х. Б. К. СИСТЕМЫ АВТОМАТИЧЕСКОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ //Universum: технические науки. – 2022. – №. 5-2 (98). – С. 45-47.
17. Tulepbergenovich K. B., Orazimbetovich U. A. Classification and analysis of computer programs for the physical preparation of athletes and expasure of prospects for their studies //European science review. – 2015. – №. 7-8. – С. 11-13.
18. Kaipbergenov A. T., Utemisov A. O., Yuldashova H. B. K. STEADY OF AUTOMATIC CONTROL SYSTEMS //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 918-921.
19. Orazimbetovich U. A. THE USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE FIELD OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2019. – Т. 7. – №. 2.
20. Djaksimuratov, K., O'razmatov, J., Yuldashev, S., Toshpulatov, D., & O'telbayev, A. (2021). Geological-Geochemical and Mineralogical Properties of Basalt Rocks of Karakalpakstan.

21. Djaksimuratov, K., O'razmatov, J., Mnajatdinov, D., & O'telbayev, A. (2021). PROPERTIES OF COAL, PROCESSES IN COAL MINING COMPANIES, METHODS OF COAL MINING IN THE WORLD.
22. Djaksimuratov, K., Toshev, O., O'razmatov, J., & O'telbayev, A. (2021). MEASURING AND CRUSHING THE STRENGTH OF ROCKS USE OF VARIOUS TYPES OF SURFACTANTS FOR GRINDING.
23. Djaksimuratov, K., Ravshanov, Z., O'razmatov, J., & O'telbayev, A. (2021). Comprehensive monitoring of surface deformation in underground mining, prevention of mining damage. Modern technologies and their role in mining.
24. Djaksimuratov, K., O'razmatov, J., Maulenov, N., & O'telbayev, A. (2021). FACTORS INFLUENCING THE CONDITIONS OF OPEN PIT MINING, ORE MASS AND DEFORMATION, PROCESSES THAT LEAD TO IMBALANCE DURING EXCAVATION.
25. Djaksimuratov, K., Jumabayeva, G., Maulenov, N., & Rametullayeva, M. (2022). Improving the Efficiency of Excavators Increasing the Efficiency of Temporary Ditch Excavator.
26. Djaksimuratov, K., Jumabayeva, G., Maulenov, N., & Rametullayeva, M. (2022). MONITORING THE CONDITION OF THE DEPOSIT IN MINING ENTERPRISES. MODERN METHODS OF DETERMINING THE LOCATION OF MINERALS.
27. Djaksimuratov, K., Joldasbayeva, A., Bayramova, M., Tolibayev, E., & Maulenov, N. (2022). TECHNOLOGICAL CLASSIFICATION OF UNDERGROUND EXCAVATION WORKS IN GEOTECHNICAL MONITORING SYSTEMS.
28. Djaksimuratov, K., Maulenov, N., Ametov, R., Rametullayeva, M., & Bayramova, M. (2022). MODERN TECHNICAL METHODS OF MONITORING LANDSLIDES IN OPEN MINES.
29. Joldasbayeva, A., Ametov, R., Embergenov, A., Maulenov, N., & Kulmuratova, A. (2022). Technology to prevent Methane or coal dust explosions in the mine.
30. Djaksimuratov, K., Maulenov, N., Rametullayeva, M., Kulmuratova, A., & Embergenov, A. (2022). Technology for Determining the Force of Impact on Buildings in the Vicinity during Blasting Operations in Mines.
31. Djaksimuratov, K., Jumabayeva, G., Maulenov, N., & Rametullayeva, M. (2022). CORROSION OF METALS AND FACTORS AFFECTING IT. METHODS OF PREVENTING CORROSION OF METALS.
32. Kulmuratova, A., Utepbaeva, G., Azizov, A., Yo'ldashova, H., & O'telbayev, A. (2022). AUTOMATION AND ROBOTIZATION OF UNDERGROUND MINES.
33. Ravshanov, Z., O'razmatov, J., Zaytova, M., Kulmuratova, A., & O'telbayev, A. (2022). Conveyor belt structure and mode of operation in mines.
34. Djaksimuratov, K., Maulenov, N., Joldasbayeva, A., O'razmatov, J., & O'telbayev, A. (2022). Model Of Stages of Determination of Strength of Dynamic Fracture of Rocks and Digital Technological Verification.
35. Djaksimuratov, K., Ravshanov, Z., Ergasheva, Z., O'razmatov, J., & O'telbayev, A. (2022). Underground mine mining systems and technological parameters of mine development.
36. Djaksimuratov, K., Maulenov, N., Joldasbayeva, A., O'razmatov, J., & O'telbayev, A. (2022). Methods of Determining the Effect of Temperature and Pressure on the Composition of Rocks.
37. Ravshanov, Z., Joldasbayeva, A., Bayramova, M., & O'telbayev, A. (2023). MINING TECHNOLOGICAL EQUIPMENT THAT DETERMINES THE SLOPE ANGLES OF THE MINE BY MEANS OF LASER BEAMS.

38. Yeshmuratova, A., Kulmuratova, A., Maulenov, N., & Otemisov, U. (2023). MINE BLASTING PROCESSES OPTIMIZATION STAGES OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY OF DETONATORS.
39. Ravshanov, Z., Joldasbayeva, A., Maulenov, N., & O'telbayev, A. (2023). Determination of mineral location coordinates in geotechnology and mining enterprises.
40. Djaksimuratov, K., Batirova, U., Otemisov, U., & Aytmuratov, S. (2023). STEPS FOR DETERMINING THE SLOPE ANGLE OF AN OPEN MINE.
41. Djaksimuratov, K., Batirova, U., Abdullaev, A., & Joldasbayeva, A. (2023). GATHERING COORDINATES OF THE GEOLOGICAL AND GEOTECHNICAL LOCATION OF THE MINE.
42. Ravshanov, Z., Joldasbayeva, A., Bayramova, M., & Madreymov, A. (2023). IN GEOLOGICAL AND GEOTECHNICAL PROCESSES IN THE MINE USE OF TECHNOLOGICAL SCANNING EQUIPMENT IN THE UNDERGROUND MINING METHOD.
43. Djaksimuratov, K., Jumabayeva, G., Maulenov, N., & Rametullayeva, M. (2022). Casting And Evaluation of Properties for an Aluminum Alloy Material and Optimizing the Quality Control Parameters.
44. Djaksimuratov, K., Jumabayeva, G., Batirova, U., & O'telbayev, A. (2023). GROUNDWATER CONTROL IN MINES
45. Abdiramanova, Z., Jumabayeva, G., Batirova, U., & O'telbayev, A. (2023). ACTIVITY OF TEBINBULAK IRON ORE MINING ENTERPRISES IN THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN.
46. Qurbonov.A.A, Djaksimuratov Karamatdin Mustapaevich, & O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li. (2021). FACTORS INFLUENCING THE CONDITIONS OF OPEN PIT MINING, ORE MASS AND DEFORMATION. PROCESSES THAT LEAD TO IMBALANCE DURING EXCAVATION. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 1(6), 45–49. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5500210>
47. O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li. (2022). STRENGTH PROPERTIES OF ROCKS AND FACTORS INFLUENCING THEM AND THE PROCESS OF CHANGING THE PROPERTIES OF ROCKS. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6034442>
48. Joldasbayeva, A., Maulenov, N., Mnajatdinov, D., & O'telbayev, A. (2023). PROCESSES OF DRAWING UP A VENTILATION SYSTEM SCHEME IN MINES.
49. Maulenov, N., Joldasbayeva, A., O'razmatov, J., & Mnajatdinov, D. (2023). TECHNOLOGICAL MODES OF MONITORING THE LOCATION OF MINES IN THE MINE AND THE SLOPE BORDER OF THE BLAST AREA.
50. Maulenov, N., Joldasbayeva, A., Amanbaev, N., & Mnajatdinov, D. (2023). PROCESSES OF BENEFICIATION AND EXTRACTION OF ORES IN IRON MINES (IN THE EXAMPLE OF TEBIN BULAK IRON MINE).
51. Maulenov, N., Joldasbayeva, A., Amanbaev, N., & Mnajatdinov, D. (2023). DETERMINATION OF VIBRATIONS CAUSED BY BLASTING PROCESSES IN OPEN PIT MINING AT MINING ENTERPRISES.
52. Maulenov, N., Joldasbayeva, A., O'razmatov, J., & Mnajatdinov, D. (2023). MOBILE TECHNOLOGICAL METHODS OF SAFETY MANAGEMENT IN SURFACE MINING.
53. Jumabayeva Guljahon Jaqsilikovna. (2023). CONTROL OF UNDERGROUND WATER IN THE MINE, DETECTION AND PREVENTION OF RISKS. ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE, 2(5), 159–166. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7648010>
54. Утемисов А. О., Юлдашова Х. Б. К. СИСТЕМЫ АВТОМАТИЧЕСКОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ //Universum: технические науки. – 2022. – №. 5-2 (98). – С. 45-47.

55. Ametov Bayram Tursynbaevich, Uzakbaeva Akmaral Sulayman Kizi, & Allamuratov Guljamal Bisengali Kizi. (2022). Wind Mill and Solar Energy. Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology, 15, 178–179. Retrieved from <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjet/article/view/3068>
56. Tolibayev Y. et al. WITH CHARGE MELTING METHODS AND LOW METAL CONTENT IN THE FURNACE EFFECT OF ELECTRODES //Международная конференция академических наук. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 151-160.
57. Tolibayev Y. et al. ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY METHODS OF MINING METAL ORES //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 45-56.
58. Tolibayev Y. et al. METHODS OF ENSURING THE INCREASE IN THE QUALITY OF EXTRACTION OF NON-FERROUS, RARE, RARE EARTH METALS //Science and innovation in the education system. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 22-31.
59. Tolibayev Y. et al. DISADVANTAGES OF TECHNOLOGICAL AUTOMATION IN METAL MELTING //Development and innovations in science. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 136-146.
60. Tolibayev Y. et al. IN METALLURGICAL PROCESS MODELING SYSTEM HIGH TEMPERATURE COPPER REFINING PROCESSES //Models and methods in modern science. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 12-22.
61. Abdiramanova Zamira Uzaqbayevna. (2023). STUDIES ON THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND PROPERTIES OF PORTLAND CEMENT. EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH, 3(3), 13–21. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7712581>
62. Najimova Nursuliw Bazarbaevna. (2023). GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT CHEMICAL PROCESSES AND REACTORS. EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH, 3(3), 28–37. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7773462>
63. Ravshanov, Z., Ergasheva, Z., Maxsitaliyeva, L., Pardaev, S., & O'telbayev, A. (2022). 3D Technological System of Management of Geological Exploration Processes of Mining Enterprises.
64. Mirzabek qizi, A. M., & Orinbay qizi, K. S. (2023). Application of Modern Microprocessors in Technological Measuring Devices and Principles of their Use. Miasto Przyszłości, 32, 320–326. Retrieved from <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1158>
65. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). Automation Technique Design Classification of Technological Objects. International Journal of Scientific Trends, 2(2), 128–136. Retrieved from <https://scientifictrends.org/index.php/ijst/article/view/66>
66. Elmurodovich T. O. et al. Measuring and crushing the strength of rocks use of various types of surfactants for grinding //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 10. – С. 557-561.
67. Djaksimuratov K. Comprehensive monitoring of surface deformation in underground mining, prevention of mining damage. Modern technologies and their role in mining //Scienceweb academic papers collection. – 2021.
68. Mustapaevich D. K. et al. FACTORS INFLUENCING THE CONDITIONS OF OPEN PIT MINING, ORE MASS AND DEFORMATION, PROCESSES THAT LEAD TO IMBALANCE DURING EXCAVATION //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 9. – №. 10. – С. 648-650.
69. Muxtar o'g'li A. R. et al. Technology to prevent Methane or coal dust explosions in the mine //The Peerian Journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – С. 22-32.

70. Axmet o'g'li M. A. et al. IN GEOLOGICAL AND GEOTECHNICAL PROCESSES IN THE MINE USE OF TECHNOLOGICAL SCANNING EQUIPMENT IN THE UNDERGROUND MINING METHOD //Intent Research Scientific Journal. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 20-27.
71. Maulenov N. et al. PROCESSES OF DRAWING UP A VENTILATION SYSTEM SCHEME IN MINES //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 161-166.
72. Maulenov N. et al. TECHNOLOGICAL MODES OF MONITORING THE LOCATION OF MINES IN THE MINE AND THE SLOPE BORDER OF THE BLAST AREA //Development and innovations in science. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 27-32.
73. Jumabayeva Guljahon Jaqsilikovna. (2023). CONTROL OF UNDERGROUND WATER IN THE MINE, DETECTION AND PREVENTION OF RISKS. ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE, 2(5), 159–166. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7648010>
74. Нажимова Н. Б. и др. ВЛИЯНИЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ И КОММУНИКАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ И ЛАБОРАТОРНОЙ МОДЕЛИ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ ХИМИИ //ЛУЧШАЯ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКАЯ РАБОТА 2021. – 2021. – С. 416-420.
75. Нажимова Н. Б. и др. ҚОРАҚАЛПОҒИСТОН ФОСФОРИТЛАРИ ВА ГЛАУКОНИТЛАРИ ТАВСИФИ ҲАМДА УЛАРНИНГ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 186-190.
76. O'telbayeva Muhayyo Alisherovna. (2023). THE PROGRAM OF APPLYING NEW PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH AND PEDAGOGICAL METHODS IN TEACHING CHEMISTRY AT SCHOOL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7785519>
77. Jumabayeva, G. . (2023). PLANNING AND MINE DESIGN IN OPEN-PIT MINING PROCESSES AT MINING ENTERPRISES. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 3(3 Part 2), 135–143. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/11147>
78. Kaipbergenov, B., & Utemisov, A. (2015). Classification and analysis of computer programs for the physical preparation of athletes and expasure of prospects for their studies.
79. Utemisov, A., & Kaipbergenov, B. (2015). ОТДЕЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЯ И ДИАГНОСТИКИ ФИЗИЧЕСКИХ НАГРУЗОК У ЗАНИМАЮЩИХСЯ СПОРТОМ (С ПРИМЕНЕНИЕМ КОМПЬЮТЕРНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ).
80. Utemisov, A. (2017). ЭЛЕКТРОН ДАРСЛИК ЗАМОНАВИЙ ЎҚУВ ЖАРАЁНИНИНГ ЭНГ АСОСИЙ ЭЛЕМЕНТИ.
81. Ильясов, А., & Utemisov, A. (2018). ИННОВАЦИОН ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАР АСОСИДА ТАЪЛИМНИ ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШ ШАКЛЛАРИ ВА ТУРЛАРИ.
82. Utemisov, A. (2019). MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TRAINING OF SPECIALISTS IN PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS.
83. Нажимова Н. Б. ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ТЕРМИЧЕСКИХ СВОЙСТВ СЫРЬЯ АСФАЛЬТОБЕТОННЫХ СМЕСЕЙ //ПРОРЫВНЫЕ НАУЧНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ, ЗАКОНОМЕРНОСТИ, ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ. – 2020. – С. 30-32.
84. Ravshanov, Z., Ergasheva, Z., Maxsitaliyeva, L., Pardaev, S., & O'telbayev, A. (2022). 3D Technological System of Management of Geological Exploration Processes of Mining Enterprises.
85. Djaksimuratov, K., O'razmatov, J., Mnajatdinov, D., & O'telbayev, A. (2021). PROPERTIES OF COAL, PROCESSES IN COAL MINING COMPANIES, METHODS OF COAL MINING IN THE WORLD.

86. Ravshanov, Z. (2022). MINING PROCESSES OF DRILLING MACHINES. INFORMATION ABOUT THE TECHNOLOGICAL ALARM SYSTEM OF DRILLING MACHINES.
87. O'telbayev, A. (2022). STRENGTH PROPERTIES OF ROCKS AND FACTORS INFLUENCING THEM AND THE PROCESS OF CHANGING THE PROPERTIES OF ROCKS. «BEST INNOVATOR IN SCIENCE - 2022» Organized by Innovative Academy. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6034441>
88. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi, Utepbaeva Gulnaz Saken qizi, O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li, Azizov Azatbek Jumabek o'g'li, & Yo'ldashova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2022). AUTOMATION AND ROBOTIZATION OF UNDERGROUND MINES. Open Access Repository, 9(10), 20–28. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/UYN93>
89. Ravshanov Zavqiddin Yahyo o'g'li, O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li, O'razmatov Jonibek Ikromboy o'g'li, Zaytova Madina Nazarbay qizi, & Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2022). Conveyor belt structure and mode of operation in mines. Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology, 11, 72–80. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejet/article/view/2360>
90. Туремуратов Ш. Н., Нажимова Н. Б. Химические и физико-химические свойства карбонатных минералов плато Устюрт //Universum: химия и биология. – 2020. – №. 10-1 (76). – С. 61-63.
91. Кадирбаев А. Б. и др. ПРИМЕР ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТРАДИЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА ИЗВЕСТИ //ПРИОРИТЕТНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. – 2021. – С. 15-17.
92. Ravshanov Zavqiddin Yahyo o'g'li, O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li, Joldasbayeva Aysulu Baxitbay qizi, & Bayramova Minevvar Axmet qizi. (2023). MINING TECHNOLOGICAL EQUIPMENT THAT DETERMINES THE SLOPE ANGLES OF THE MINE BY MEANS OF LASER BEAMS. Neo Scientific Peer Reviewed Journal, 6, 17–23. Retrieved from <https://neojournals.com/index.php/nspj/article/view/96>
93. Нажимова Н. Б. и др. РОЛЬ МИНЕРАЛЬНОГО НАПОЛНИТЕЛЯ В АСФАЛЬТОВОЙ СМЕСИ //МОЛОДОЙ УЧЁНЫЙ. – 2021. – С. 15-18.
94. Ravshanov Zavqiddin Yahyo o'g'li, Joldasbayeva Aysulu Baxitbay qizi, Maulenov Nurlibek Axmet o'g'li, & O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li. (2023). Determination of mineral location coordinates in geotechnology and mining enterprises. Global Scientific Review, 11, 8–14. Retrieved from <http://scientificreview.com/index.php/gsr/article/view/134>
95. Uteniyazov, A. K., Leyderman, A. Y., Gafurova, M. V., Juraev, K. N., & Dauletov, K. A. (2021). The effect of ultrasonic treatments on current transport processes in Al-Al₂O₃-p-CdTe-Mo structure. Advances in Materials Science and Engineering, 2021, 1-6.
96. Dauletov K. A. et al. A heat-resistant Schottky diode based on Ge/GaAs heterosystem //Poverkhnost. – 1999. – №. 3. – С. 60-62.
97. Закиров М. М. и др. Современное состояние подземных вод Каракалпакского Устюрта. – 2022.
98. Курбанов А. А., Джаксымуратов К., Отелбаев А. ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ БАЗАЛЬТОВЫХ ПОРОД В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 3-2 (82). – С. 61-65.
99. O'telbayeva, M. ., & O'telbayev, A. . (2023). EXPERIMENTAL WORKS BASED ON ADVANCED, PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL AND MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING

CHEMISTRY AT SCHOOL. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 3(3),
79–88. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/11332>

